

Analysis of an Online Shopping Satisfaction Model that Impact on Increasing Retraction Intention

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Abstract:- This research aims to determine and analyze the effect of perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, perceived price, and e-service quality on e-repurchase intention to the Shopee marketplace application, either directly or indirectly through e-satisfaction. The population in this research are users of the Shopee marketplace application services located in Jabodetabek. Sampling was carried out using purposive sampling, with the criteria of consumers who are in Jabodetabek and have made online shopping transactions at least twice on the Shopee marketplace application within six months. The sample size is 171 respondents. The structural equation model was chosen as the analysis method. The results of this research showed perceived usefulness, perceived price and e-service quality have a positive and significant effect on e-satisfaction, while perceived ease of use has a positive and insignificant effect on e-satisfaction. There is a positive and significant influence between e-satisfaction, perceived ease of use and perceived price with e-repurchase intention, perceived usefulness have a positive and insignificant effect on e-repurchase intention and then e-service quality does not have a positive and insignificant effect on e-repurchase intention. Furthermore, e-satisfaction plays a role in mediating the relationship between perceived usefulness, perceived price, and e-service quality on e-repurchase intention.

Keywords:- Perceived Ease of use, Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Price, E-Service Quality, E-Repurchase Intention, Shopee Marketplace.

I. INTRODUCTION

At the beginning of its development, the internet was only used for military, academic and certain corporate purposes, where the internet was used only for sending electronic mail (e-mail). However, along with the development of hardware and software which is very fast and supported by ADSL (Asymmetric Digital Subscriber Line) technology, making the internet a primary, primary and important need in all fields that can be enjoyed 24-hour internet access with more complete internet services offered. communicative and pampering consumers in the sense of internet access. The material delivered via the internet web is also experiencing very rapid development, where the material made is not limited to just text, but can also be in the form of images, sound, video, streaming, to

interactive ones, such as chatting, video conferencing, and so on. . At present, the online digital world has touched all aspects of life to simplify and speed up work so that it becomes effective and efficient (Sumargono, 2011).

Based on data from the Association of Indonesian Internet Service Providers or APJII for 2022, it is known that the growth of internet users in Indonesia is growing quite rapidly where it experiences a significant increase every year as shown in Figure 1.

Fig 1 Growth of Internet Users in Indonesia
Source: APJII Report (2022)

Based on the graph above, it can be concluded that the growth of internet users in Indonesia increased from 2021 to 2022 by 77.02 percent, meaning that internet use was very high during the COVID-19 pandemic both in terms of online shopping transactions, online teaching and learning processes, information search and use of entertainment (social media). Based on these figures, the effects of this pandemic have had a very significant impact on internet users in Indonesia. In addition, many business players take advantage of these conditions as online shopping application service innovations through marketplaces and digital payment system service innovations, considering that the majority of people are at home, so many use online shopping and electronic payments.

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused major changes in consumer behavior or what is called Megashift Consumer Behavior (Yuswohady, 2021). Yuswohady further (2021) explains that changes in consumer behavior that occurred during the pandemic, such as increases in online purchases

and application usage, are expected to continue even after the pandemic ends. This is because the pandemic has increased awareness and trust in online services, as well as increased reliance on technology and the convenience of shopping online. At least the implementation of large-scale social restrictions (PSBB) has had a significant impact on community activities where activities that are usually carried out outside the home have turned into activities inside the home (work from home, online teaching and learning processes and online shopping transactions). This creates a new phenomenon in which there is an increase in the need for the internet, the use of digital money, and online shopping habits.

Based on data from the Association of Indonesian Internet Service Providers or APJII for 2022, as shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3, internet services that were widely used by Indonesians during the COVID-19 pandemic were (1) video conferencing for business activities, online teaching and learning processes (e.g. -learning), (2) E-commerce services (online shopping) to fulfill online buying and selling transactions and (3) Social Media Services (Tiktok, YouTube, IG) as entertainment. While the ten provinces with high levels of internet usage for online shopping are (1) DKI Jakarta, (2) Aceh, (3) North Kalimantan, (4) West Sumatra, (5) Jambi, (6) Bengkulu, (7) Sulawesi South, (8) Central Java, (9) Lampung and (10) South Sumatra.

Fig 2 Internet Usage During the COVID-19 Pandemic
Source: APJII Report (2022)

Fig 3 10 Provinces with High Internet Usage Rates for Online Shopping
Source: APJII Report (2022)

Meanwhile, based on Priceza's findings in 2022, there are five major cities in Indonesia which are the main sources of visits (traffic) to various online stores, namely Jakarta, Surabaya, Medan, Bandung and Makassar. For 3 years in a row, the composition of city names which are the main source of visits has not changed at all. This composition also ranks almost consistently according to the order and the order of these cities also reflects the ranking in terms of population. This shows that internet penetration in big cities in Indonesia is quite high and evenly distributed so that many citizens use the internet to shop online through applications because they are very familiar with technology.

With the increasing use of the internet during the COVID-19 pandemic, changes in the lifestyle of Indonesian people have also experienced changes in terms of buying and selling activities. What was originally carried out conventionally, namely buying and selling transactions carried out offline, became buying and selling transactions carried out online using the marketplace. Marketplace is an online buying and selling platform that helps sellers market their products, thus providing consumers with a variety of products and online shops with only one place to access. In Indonesia itself, there are several marketplaces that are already operating, such as the Shopee, Tokopedia, Lazada, Bukalapak and BliBli marketplaces.

Based on a survey conducted by Iprice in 2022, where there is very tight marketplace competition in terms of the number of visits to the marketplace, the number of marketplace users and the number of online transactions in the marketplace. Iprice further (2022) explains that the Shopee marketplace in Indonesia is the highest marketplace in terms of the number of visitors and the total number of online transactions compared to other marketplaces.

This can be seen from the average number of visitors per month reaching 71.5 million in the first quarter of 2020, an increase of 129.3 million visitors in the first quarter of 2021 and continuing to increase by 138.7 million visitors in the fourth quarter of 2021 as shown in Figure 4.

Fig 4 Number of Monthly Marketplace Visitors in Indonesia
Source: Iprice (2022)

This indicates that the Shopee marketplace application is the marketplace that is most in demand and visited by consumers during the pandemic and after the COVID-19 pandemic

Besides that, the Shopee marketplace application has increased its market share in the number of online shopping transactions (share of orders) by 41 percent in 2021 compared to other online shopping applications, as shown in Figure 5. This indicates that the Shopee marketplace application is the new online shopping application that is most in demand by the people of Indonesia.

Fig 5 Percentage of the Number of Online Shopping Transactions in 2021
Source: Ipsos (2022)

Based on topbrandaward.com data for 2022, the Shopee application will rank first in terms of top brand marketplaces in 2021 and 2022, as shown in Figure 6.

TOP BRAND SITUS ONLINE SHOPPING / MARKETPLACE					
BRAND	TBI 2020	BRAND	TBI 2021	BRAND	TBI 2022
Lazada.co.id	31.9% TOP	Shopee.co.id	41.8% TOP	Shopee.co.id	43.7% TOP
Shopee.co.id	20.0% TOP	Tokopedia.com	16.7% TOP	Tokopedia.com	14.9% TOP
Tokopedia.com	15.8% TOP	Lazada.co.id	15.2% TOP	Lazada.co.id	14.7% TOP
Bukalapak.com	12.5%	Bukalapak.com	9.5%	BliBli.com	10.1%
BliBli.com	8.4%	BliBli.com	8.1%	Bukalapak.com	8.1%

Fig 6 Top Brand Index Marketplace Sites in Indonesia
Source: topbrandaward.com (2022)

Based on the data above, the Shopee application in 2020 ranked second in the top brand marketplace of 20%, while in 2021 the Shopee marketplace application ranked first in the top brand marketplace of 41.8% as well as in 2022 the Shopee marketplace application ranked first at 43.3%. This indicates that Indonesian people prefer to shop online using the Shopee marketplace application compared to other online shopping applications. Considering that the

Shopee marketplace application often carries out promotional activities in the form of free shipping and massive discounts on products sold at Shopee.

Based on Statista data for 2022 as shown in Figure 7 where the number of online shopping transactions on the Shopee marketplace application has increased from the 1st quarter of 2020 to the 4th quarter of 2021 amounting to 1.6 billion rupiah but in the 1st quarter of 2022 the number of online shopping transactions on Shopee decreased by 100 million rupiah. This indicates that the high interest of the Indonesian people in conducting online shopping transactions using the Shopee platform. In addition, it can also be concluded that the majority of Shopee service users are satisfied with online shopping transactions, thus allowing Shopee service users to make online shopping transactions more than twice.

Fig 7 Number of Online Shopping Transactions at Shopee from Quarter 1 of 2020 to Quarter 2 of 2022
Source: Statista (2022)

The need for Shopee marketplace management to increase customer satisfaction in using Shopee services in order to increase the number of visits and the number of transactions. This is reinforced by the results of research which states that online shopping satisfaction has a positive and significant influence on the intention to return online shopping transactions (Tandon et al., 2017; Liang et al., 2018; Risco et al., 2022; Hardiyanto and Firdaus, 2021).

This indicates that it is necessary for online shopping management to conduct a study on the satisfaction of online shopping services. Given the high competition among fellow online shopping applications in increasing the number of users and the number of online shopping transactions. So researchers need to do research on the determinants of customer satisfaction in online shopping. In this case, the object of research is the Shopee marketplace application.

The researcher conducted a pre-survey in September 2022 by describing twenty factors that were thought to be determining factors for online shopping satisfaction using the Shopee marketplace application to 30 male and female respondents who usually make online transactions using the

Shopee marketplace application. The researcher asked respondents to provide an assessment of twenty factors that could influence online shopping satisfaction through the Shopee marketplace application. Assessment uses a Likert's scale with intervals of 1 to 5 which starts from 1 (strongly disagree), 2 (disagree), 3 (not in favor), 4 (agree), and 5 (strongly agree). Furthermore, the researcher will process the pre-survey data by averaging the value of each factor selected by the respondents.

Based on the results of pre-survey data processing, there are four main or top factors which are the determining variables (cause) of respondents' satisfaction with using the Shopee marketplace application in conducting transactions or shopping online, namely (1) Ease of use of Shopee marketplace application services (perceived ease of use) , (2) The perceived benefits of using the Shopee marketplace application (perceived usefulness), (3) Online product prices on the Shopee marketplace (perceived price) and (4) Online service quality from the Shopee marketplace (e-service quality) as seen in figure 8.

Figure 8 Determining Factors Based on Pre-Survey Results
 Source: Results of Pre-Survey Data Processing by Researchers (2022)

Table 1 Results of Determinants of Online Shopping Satisfaction Using the Shopee Application

S No.	Hasil Mapping Jurnal (Faktor Penentu Kepuasan Berbelanja Online Menggunakan Aplikasi Shopee)	Hasil Pra Survey (Faktor Penentu Kepuasan Berbelanja Online Menggunakan Aplikasi Shopee)
1.	Kemudahan Penggunaan (<i>Perceived Ease of Use</i>)	Kemudahan Penggunaan Aplikasi
2.	Manfaat/Kegunaan (<i>Perceived Usefulness</i>)	Manfaat Yang Dirasakan
3.	Kepercayaan (<i>Trust</i>)	Harga
4.	Promosi (<i>Promotion</i>)	Kualitas Layanan <i>Online</i>
5.	Citra Merek (<i>Brand Image</i>)	Kepercayaan Terhadap Aplikasi
6.	Kesenangan Dirasakan (<i>Perceived Enjoyment</i>)	Iklan dan Promosi
7.	Kualitas Produk (<i>Product Quality</i>)	Citra Merek
8.	Keamanan (<i>Perceived Security</i>)	Kesenangan Terhadap Aplikasi
9.		Ketersediaan dan Kelayakan Produk
10.		Pilihan Produk Luas dan Beragam
11.		Kemudahan Fitur Pencarian Produk
12.		Jaminan Keamanan Transaksi
13.		Orang Terdekat
14.		Sudah Terbiasa Belanja <i>Online</i>
15.		Perbincangan di Media Sosial (<i>eWOM</i>)
16.		<i>Brand Ambassador</i>
17.		Rekomendasi Pihak Lain
18.		Resiko Belanja <i>Online</i> Kecil
19.		Ketersediaan Produk Favorit
20.		Kecepatan Respon Komplain

Source: Results of Pre-Survey Data Processing by Researchers (2022)

Based on the mapping results of previous studies related to online shopping satisfaction, it was found that the majority of researchers previously examined the determinants of customer satisfaction, namely service benefits (perceived usefulness) and perceived ease of use (Asmarina et al., 2022; Oktarini and Wardana, 2021; Wilson et al., 2021; Dewi et al., 2020; Basyar and Sanaji, 2018; Wiwoho, 2018; Santona et al., 2021; Juniwati and Sumiyati, 2020; Prasetya, 2022; Tandon and Sah, 2017; Kahar et al., 2018; Wilson, 2019; Ferdianto and Hendar, 2022; Trivedi and Yadav, 2019; Febriani and Ardani, 2021; Syaharani and Yasa, 2022; Jatimoyo et al., 2021; Yanico and Keni, 2021; Ching et al., 2021). This indicates that the ease of use of online shopping services and the benefits of online services are the main factors that have been studied by several previous researchers.

Based on the data in table 1 above, the majority of respondents answered the ease of using the Shopee marketplace application and the perceived benefits of using the Shopee marketplace application as a determining factor for respondents' satisfaction in shopping online through the use of the Shopee marketplace application. So researchers need to review these two factors as factors that cause satisfaction with the Shopee marketplace application service. In addition, the researchers added two other factors from the results of the pre-survey, namely online service quality (e-service quality) and online product prices (perceived price) as factors causing the satisfaction of the Shopee marketplace application service in transacting or shopping online.

Satisfied consumers using online shopping application services will have an impact on the reuse of online shopping application services both in terms of increasing the number of transactions and increasing the frequency of using online shopping application services again. For this reason, researchers need to study the impact of online shopping service application user satisfaction on the reuse of online shopping services. This is reinforced by the results of previous literature studies which state that satisfied customers using online shopping service applications can increase the reuse of online shopping services and increase the number of transactions in the application (Kahar et al., 2018; Wilson, 2019; Ferdianto and Hendar, 2022; Liang et al., 2018; Risco et al., 2022; Hardiyanto and Firdaus, 2021; Basyar and Sanaji, 2018; Asmarina et al., 2022; Trivedi and Yadav, 2019; Juniwati and Sumiyati, 2020; Antwi, 2021; Febriani and Ardani, 2021; Wilson et al., 2021; Oktarini and Wardana, 2021; Wiwoho, 2018; Dewi et al., 2020; Yanico and Keni, 2021; Hardiyanto and Firdaus, 2021; Jatimoyo et al., 2021; Prasetya, 2022; Syaharani and Yasa, 2022; Kristanto and Firdausy, 2021; Wafiyah, and Kusumadewi, 2021; Santona et al., 2021; Rita et al. 2019).

Based on the literature study above and the results of the pre-survey, researchers need to conduct an in-depth study of the customer satisfaction model of the Shopee marketplace service which has an impact on the reuse of the Shopee marketplace service to make transactions or shop online.

II. THEORITICAL REVIEW

➤ *E-commerce*

E-commerce can provide a sense of security and convenience in transactions (Mastisia, 2019). According to Kotler and Armstrong (2012), E-commerce allows customers to make transactions or shop online 24 hours a day from almost every location where consumers are. Kotler & Keller (2016) in Amalia (2022), said that consumer behavior must be understood correctly because, if the product consumed meets consumer expectations and provides pleasure and satisfaction, it will foster consumer intention to repurchase (repurchase intention) or interact indirectly. continuously or continuously using a product (continuance intention) (Larassita et al., 2019).

➤ *Technology Continuance Theory (TCT)*

Technology Continuance Theory (TCT) is a new theory in explaining user behavior towards technology continuance introduced by Liao, Palvia, and Chen (2009). This theory integrates three models, namely the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1986), Expectation Confirmation Model (ECM) (Bhattacharjee, 2001), and Cognitive Model (COG) (Oliver, 1980).

➤ *Concept Perceived Ease of use*

Starting with the research of Davis et al. (1989), who found that perceived ease of use has a role in influencing user intentions for a particular system to be used. Furthermore, Davis (1989) defines perceived ease of use as a perception that refers to the extent to which a user believes that the use of a technology or system can make it easier for users and free from problems.

According to Wilson (2019) states that perceived ease of use is a customer's assessment of the amount of effort a customer has to spend in learning and using a new technology or system.

➤ *Concept Perceived Usefulness*

Davis (1989) defines perceived usefulness as "the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance". Davis (1989) defines perceived benefit as the extent to which a person believes that using a particular system will improve his job performance. According to Ferdianto and Hendar (2022) the perceived benefits are the core structure of the Technology Acceptance Model.

Perceived benefits can be defined as customers' judgments and perceptions about whether the new system they use will give them added value compared to the old system (Wilson, 2019).

➤ *Concept Perceived Price*

According to Tjiptono quoted in Ruffiansah and Seno (2020) defining product prices from a marketing point of view, prices are monetary units or other actions (including other goods and services) that are exchanged in order to obtain ownership rights or use of an item or service. Puryanto (2021) and Ruffiansah & Seno (2020) state that

price is one of the most flexible elements of the marketing mix, meaning it can be changed quickly. Pricing is a way to differentiate its offering from competitors (Sintya et al., 2018).

➤ *Concept E-Service Quality*

According to Wijaya and Astuti (2018) argued that service quality is generally defined as the level of service provided in accordance with customer expectations. Service quality, both online and offline, is an important marketing strategy to provide the best service as a competitive advantage for companies. According to Jaya et al. (2021) in Puryanto (2021) defines that service quality is something that service providers must do well. Service quality as perceived by consumers, comes from a comparison between what is offered by a service company, namely expectations and with their perceptions of the service provider's performance.

➤ *Concept E-Satisfaction*

Satisfaction is a key factor for consumers in making repeat purchases, which is the largest portion of the company's sales volume (Tubagus, 2018). This means that consumers who are satisfied with online products tend to repurchase products and reuse services when the same need arises again in the future. Customer satisfaction according to Kotler (2018: 39) is based on something that is relatively felt by the buyer for the performance of the goods/services that have been consumed and then compared with the expectations of the buyer for the goods/services. Customer satisfaction can be defined as a consumer's perception or assessment of the company's ability to meet or exceed the expectations that consumers have for the company (Wilson et al., 2019).

➤ *Concept E-Repurchase Intention*

The occurrence of post-purchase consumer satisfaction and dissatisfaction with a product will influence subsequent behavior. If consumers are satisfied, they will show a higher probability of repurchasing the product (Kotler & Keller, 2012).

Online repurchase intention (e-repurchase intention) is closely related to consumer attitudes towards objects and consumer attitudes towards previous behavior (Kristanto and Firdausy, 2021). According to Chiu et al. in Santona et al. (2021) an online shopping process with a simple procedure will increase consumer intention to make a repurchase. The intention to re-transaction in online shopping is influenced by many factors.

III. FRAMEWORK

Fig 9 The Proposed Research Model
Source: Data processed by researchers (2022)

➤ Based on Figure 9 regarding the research model proposed above, the research hypothesis is as follows:

- The first hypothesis (H1) is that Perceived Ease of Use has a positive and significant effect on Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) in the Shopee marketplace.
- The second hypothesis (H2) is Perceived Usefulness has a positive and significant effect on Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) in the Shopee marketplace.
- The third hypothesis (H3) is Perceived Price of Online Products (Perceived Price) has a positive and significant effect on Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) in the Shopee marketplace.
- The fourth hypothesis (H4) is that Online Service Quality (E-Service Quality) has a positive and significant effect on Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) in the Shopee marketplace.
- The fifth hypothesis (H5) is Perceived Ease of Use has a positive and significant effect on Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention) using the Shopee marketplace application.
- The sixth hypothesis (H6) is Perceived Usefulness has a positive and significant effect on Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention) using the Shopee marketplace application.
- The seventh hypothesis (H7) is Perceived Price of Online Products (Perceived Price) has a positive and significant effect on Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention) using the Shopee marketplace application.
- The eighth hypothesis (H8) is that Online Service Quality (E-Service Quality) has a positive and significant effect on Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention) using the Shopee marketplace application.

- The ninth hypothesis (H9) is that Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) has a positive and significant effect on Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention) using the Shopee marketplace application.
- The tenth hypothesis (H10) is Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) mediates the relationship between Perceived ease of use and Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention) using the Shopee marketplace application.
- The eleventh hypothesis (H11): Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) mediates the relationship between Perceived usefulness and E-Repurchase Intention using the Shopee marketplace application.
- The twelfth hypothesis (H12): Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) mediates the relationship between Perceived Price and Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention) using the Shopee marketplace application.
- The thirteenth hypothesis (H13): Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) mediates the relationship between Online Service Quality (E-Service Quality) and Online Shopping Transaction Intention (E-Repurchase Intention) using the Shopee marketplace application.

IV. RESEARCH METHODS

➤ *Research Design*

The type of research used is associative quantitative, namely research that tests the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable. So the research method used is explanatory survey. The variables to be tested are independent variables including Perceived Ease of Use (X1), Perceived Usefulness (X2), Perceived Price of Online Products (X3) and Quality of Online Services (E-Service Quality) (X4) while the dependent variable in this study includes Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) (Y1) and E-Repurchase Intention (Y2).

➤ *Population and Sample*

The population in this study are users of the Shopee marketplace application service in Jabodetabek. This was done considering that Jabodetabek is one of the five largest cities and has high online shopping capabilities (APJII, 2022; Priceza, 2022). According to Hair, Anderson, Tatham, & Black (2010) stated that a sample size that is too large will make it difficult to obtain a suitable model, and it is recommended that an appropriate sample size be between 100-200 respondents so that estimation interpretation can be used with the Structural Equation Model (SEM). The number of users of the Shopee marketplace application service who have made transactions at least twice is not known with certainty, so in determining the number of samples the researcher used the Hair et al (2010) formula, namely:

- $n = (\text{Total Number of Indicators} \times 5)$
- So that the total number of samples in this study amounted to:
- $n = 33 \times 5 = 165$ respondents

Based on the formula Hair et al (2010) above, the maximum number of samples in this study was 165 respondents. The sampling method used in this study was non-probability sampling, namely purposive sampling with the following respondent requirements: (1) Jabodetabek residents (2) have made online shopping transactions at least twice on the shopee application in the last 6 months.

➤ *Data Collection Methods*

This study uses two types of data, namely:

- Primary data obtained from respondents' assessment of research variables namely Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Price, Online Service Quality (E-Service Quality), Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) and Repurchase Intention on the Shopee marketplace application.
- Secondary data in the form of conditions of online shopping behavior in Indonesia, the number of users and the number of online shopping transactions in Indonesia and data on top e-commerce brands in Indonesia.
- Data collection techniques used in this study are:

- For primary data collection using structured and closed interview techniques using questionnaires distributed online via the Google form to users of the Shopee application service.
- For secondary data collection, the researcher uses literature study techniques obtained both from internet media sourced from websites and previous research journal reports.

➤ *Descriptive Analysis and Data Analysis Methods*

Researchers used descriptive statistical analysis in the form of calculating the average value of each research variable. Given the answers to each research variable question using a Likert scale (ordinal scale) so that the average rating of each variable is said to be good if it has a value above 4. As for the assessment of the characteristics of the respondents, the researcher used descriptive statistical analysis of frequency using excel software. Taking into account the limitations of the sample and research time, the method used in this study uses the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) Analysis method using the Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis tool with SmartPLS 3.0 software to process and analyze the results of the data that has been collected.

V. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

➤ *Uji Collinierity Statistics*

Table 2 Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) Test Results

Variabel	<i>E-Repurchase Intention</i>	<i>E-Satisfaction</i>	<i>E-Service Quality</i>	<i>Perceived Ease of Use</i>	<i>Perceived Price</i>	<i>Perceived Usefulness</i>
<i>E-Repurchase Intention</i>						
<i>E-Satisfaction</i>	2,659					
<i>E-Service Quality</i>	2,543	2,742				
<i>Perceived Ease of Use</i>	2,227	2,224				
<i>Perceived Price</i>	2,602	2,412				
<i>Perceived Usefulness</i>	2,848	2,664				

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS, 2023

Based on table 2 above, it can be seen that the overall variance inflation factor (VIF) value for each indicator is <3.3, so it can be said that the data does not have collinearity problems.

➤ *Koefisien Determinasi R-Square (R²)*

Table 3 Results of r-Square Values

Variabel	<i>r-Square</i>	<i>r-Square Adjusted</i>
<i>E-Satisfaction</i>	0.727	0.720
<i>E-Repurchase Intention</i>	0.790	0.784

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS, 2023

Based on table 3 above, it can be seen that the r-Square value of the E-Satisfaction (M) variable is 0.727 with an Adjusted r-Square value of 0.720, it can be explained that all independent variables Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Price and E -Service Quality simultaneously influences or can explain the E-Satisfaction variable by 72%. The rest, about 28% can be explained by other variables outside those studied. Because the Adjusted r-Square is close to the value of 75%, the influence of all independent variable constructs on E-Satisfaction is strong.

Meanwhile, the r-Square value of the E-Repurchase Intention (Y) variable is 0.790 with an Adjusted r-Square value of 0.784, it can be explained that the variables Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Price, E-Service Quality and E-Satisfaction simultaneously influencing or being able to explain the E-Repurchase Intention variable of 78.4% while the remaining 21.6% is explained by other variables outside those studied. Because the Adjusted r-Square is more than 75%, the influence of all independent variable constructs on E-Repurchase Intention is strong. Thus it can be said that the greater the r-Square number indicates the greater the independent variable can explain the dependent variable so that the structural equation model is good.

➤ *Koefisien Determinasi F-Square (f2)*

Table 4 Results of f-Square Values

Variabel	E-Repurchase Intention	Kesimpulan	E-Satisfaction	Kesimpulan
E-Repurchase Intention				
E-Satisfaction	0,595	Tinggi		
E-Service Quality	0,022	Rendah	0,292	Tinggi
Perceived Ease of Use	0,030	Rendah	0,002	Rendah
Perceived Price	0,087	Rendah	0,079	Rendah
Perceived Usefulness	0,012	Rendah	0,069	Rendah

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS, 2023

Based on table 4 regarding the results of the f-Square (f2) value above, it can be seen that the E-Satisfaction variable for E-Repurchase Intention produces an f2 value of 0.595, so the effect is relatively high. The E-Service Quality variable on the E-Satisfaction variable produces an f2 value of 0.292, so the effect is relatively high. The Perceived Ease Of Use variable on the E-Satisfaction variable produces an f2 value of 0.002, so the effect is relatively low. The Perceived Usefulness variable on the E-Satisfaction variable produces an f2 value of 0.069, so the effect is relatively low. While the Perceived Price variable on the E-Satisfaction variable has a value of f2 of 0.079, the effect is classified as moderate.

➤ *Uji Nilai Predictive Relevance (Q-Square)*

Table 5 Cross-Validated Redundancy Test Results

Variable	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)
E-Satisfaction	1539.000	765.454	0.503
E-Repurchase Intention	513.000	168.283	0.672
E-Service Quality	2052.000	2052.000	
Perceived Ease of Use	513.000	513.000	
Perceived Price	513.000	513.000	
Perceived Usefulness	513.000	513.000	

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS, 2023

Based on table 5 regarding the results of the Cross-validated Redundancy Test it can be explained that the value Q² of 0.503 and 0.662. Because the value is greater than 0, the model has predictive relevance.

➤ *Uji Model Fit*

Table 6 Results of the Fit Model Test

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.066	0.066
d_ ULS	2.420	2.420
d_ G	1.444	1.444
Chi-Square	1281.867	1281.867
NFI	0.768	0.768

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS, 2023

Based on table 6 above, it can be seen that the SRMR (Standardized Root Mean Square Residual) value of 0.066 is less than 0.09 so that the model is appropriate or meets the fit model criteria. Meanwhile, the NFI value of 0.768 is greater than 0.5 so that it can be said that the model meets the criteria for the Fit model.

➤ Estimate for Path Coefficients

Table 7 Path Coefficients Analysis Results

Variabel	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Keterangan	Hasil
Direct Effect atau Pengaruh Langsung							
<i>Perceived Ease of Use -> E-Satisfaction</i>	0.032	0.034	0.065	0.493	0,622	Tidak Signifikan	Ditolak
<i>Perceived Usefulness -> E-Satisfaction</i>	0.224	0.225	0.077	2.924	0,004	Signifikan	Diterima
<i>Perceived Price -> E-Satisfaction</i>	0.228	0.230	0.073	3.111	0,002	Signifikan	Diterima
<i>E-Service Quality -> E-Satisfaction</i>	0.468	0.466	0.092	5.098	0,000	Signifikan	Diterima
<i>Perceived Ease of Use -> E-Repurchase Intention</i>	0.118	0.115	0.058	2.058	0,040	Signifikan	Diterima
<i>Perceived Usefulness -> E-Repurchase Intention</i>	0.084	0.081	0.073	1.153	0,249	Tidak Signifikan	Ditolak
<i>Perceived Price -> E-Repurchase Intention</i>	0.217	0.212	0.052	4.148	0,000	Signifikan	Diterima
<i>E-Service Quality -> E-Repurchase Intention</i>	-0.128	-0.117	0.079	1.626	0,105	Tidak Signifikan	Ditolak
<i>E-Satisfaction -> E-Repurchase Intention</i>	0.676	0.674	0.082	8.269	0,000	Signifikan	Diterima
Indirect Effect atau Pengaruh Tidak Langsung							
<i>Perceived Ease of Use -> E-Satisfaction -> E-Repurchase Intention</i>	0.022	0.024	0.045	0.484	0.629	Tidak Memedi asi	Ditolak
<i>Perceived Usefulness -> E-Satisfaction -> E-Repurchase Intention</i>	0.151	0.152	0.057	2.638	0.009	Signifikan	Diterima
<i>Perceived Price -> E-Satisfaction -> E-Repurchase Intention</i>	0.154	0.157	0.056	2.725	0.007	Signifikan	Diterima
<i>E-Service Quality -> E-Satisfaction -> E-Repurchase Intention</i>	0.316	0.311	0.060	5.282	0.000	Signifikan	Diterima

Sumber: Data diolah dengan SmartPLS, 2023

Based on table 7 above, it can be seen that the path coefficient values that can be seen in the original sample column have a range from -0.128 to 0.676. Thus it can be concluded that there is one path that has a negative relationship because it has a value away from +1 and there are eight paths that have a positive relationship because it has a value close to +1.

Based on table 7 above, it also illustrates the value of the results of hypothesis testing which is done by looking at the path coefficients based on the significance value of the t-statistic and the value of the t-statistic, so it can be described as in Figure 10 below.

Fig 10 Influence Test Model

➤ Based on the results of statistical calculations in table 7 above, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The first hypothesis (H1) is that Perceived Ease of Use has a positive and significant effect on Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction). Based on table 7, the variable Perceived Ease of Use has a positive and insignificant effect on Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) as seen from the original sample of 0.032, a P value of 0.622 > 0.05, and a T statistic of 0.493 < 1.96. So, it can be concluded that the first hypothesis is rejected.
- The second hypothesis (H2) is Perceived Usefulness has a positive and significant effect on Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction). Based on table 7, the variable Perceived Usefulness has a positive and significant effect on Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) as seen from the original sample of 0.224, a P value of 0.004 < 0.05, and a T statistic of 2.924 > 1.96. So, it can be concluded that the second hypothesis is accepted.

- The third hypothesis (H3) is Perceived Price of Online Products (Perceived Price) has a positive and significant effect on Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction). Based on table 7, the variable Perceived Price of Online Products (Perceived Price) has a positive and significant effect on Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) as seen from the original sample of 0.228, a P value of 0.002 < 0.05, and a T statistic of 3.111 > 1.96. So, it can be concluded that the third hypothesis is accepted.
- The fourth hypothesis (H4) is that Online Service Quality (E-Service Quality) has a positive and significant effect on Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction). Based on table 7, the variable Online Service Quality (E-Service Quality) has a positive and significant effect on Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) as seen from the original sample of 0.468, a P value of 0.000 < 0.05, and a T statistic of 5.098 > 1.96. So, it can be concluded that the fourth hypothesis is accepted.

- The fifth hypothesis (H5) is Perceived Ease of Use (Perceived Ease of Use) has a positive and significant effect on Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention). Based on table 7, the variable Perceived Ease of Use has a positive and significant effect on Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention) as seen from the original sample of 0.118, P value of 0.040 <0.05, and T statistic of 2.058 > 1.96. So, it can be concluded that the fifth hypothesis is accepted.
- The sixth hypothesis (H6) is Perceived Usefulness has a positive and significant effect on Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention). Based on table 7, the variable Perceived Usefulness has a positive and not significant effect on Intention of Online Shopping Transactions Again (E-Repurchase Intention) as seen from the original sample of 0.084, P value of 0.249 > 0.05, and T statistic of 1.153 < 1.96. So, it can be concluded that the sixth hypothesis is rejected.
- The seventh hypothesis (H7) is Perceived Price of Online Products (Perceived Price) has a positive and significant effect on Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention). Based on table 7, the variable Perceived Price of Online Products (Perceived Price) has a positive and significant effect on Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention) as seen from the original sample of 0.217, a P value of 0.000 <0.05, and a T statistic of 4.148 > 1.96. So, it can be concluded that the seventh hypothesis is accepted.
- The eighth hypothesis (H8) is that Online Service Quality (E-Service Quality) has a positive and significant effect on Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention). Based on table 7, the variable Online Service Quality (E-Service Quality) has a negative and not significant effect on Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention) as seen from the original sample of -0.128, P value of 0.105 > 0.05, and T statistic of 1.626 < 1.96. So, it can be concluded that the eighth hypothesis is rejected.
- The ninth hypothesis (H9) is Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) has a positive and significant effect on Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention). Based on table 7, the variable Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) has a positive and significant effect on Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention) as seen from the original sample of 0.676, P value of 0.000 <0.05, and T statistic of 8.269 > 1.96. So, it can be concluded that the ninth hypothesis is accepted.
- The tenth hypothesis (H10) is Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) mediates the relationship between Perceived Ease of Use and Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention). Based on table 7, the variable Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) does not mediate between Perceived Ease of Use and Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention) as seen from the original sample of 0.022, P value of 0.629 > 0.05, and the T statistic is 0.484 < 1.96. So, it can be concluded that the tenth hypothesis is rejected.
- The eleventh hypothesis (H11) is Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) mediates the relationship between Perceived Usefulness and Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention). Based on table 7, the variable Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) mediates between Perceived Usefulness and Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention) as seen from the original sample of 0.151, a P value of 0.009 <0.05, and The T statistic is 2.638 > 1.96. So, it can be concluded that the eleventh hypothesis is accepted.
- The twelfth hypothesis (H12) is Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) mediates the relationship between Perceived Price and Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention). Based on table 7, the variable Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) mediates between Perceived Price of Online Products (Perceived Price) and Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention) as seen from the original sample of 0.154, P value of 0.007 <0.05, and T statistics of 2.725 > 1.96. So, it can be concluded that the twelfth hypothesis is accepted.
- The thirteenth hypothesis (H13) is Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) mediates the relationship between Online Service Quality (E-Service Quality) and Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention). Based on table 7, the variable Online Shopping Satisfaction (E-Satisfaction) mediates between Online Service Quality (E-Service Quality) and Intention to Return Online Shopping Transactions (E-Repurchase Intention) as seen from the original sample of 0.316, P value of 0.000 <0.05, and the T statistic is 5.282 > 1.96. So, it can be concluded that the thirteenth hypothesis is accepted.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the introduction, the discussion in the previous chapter and the results of the analysis of the discussion regarding "Online Shopping Satisfaction Model Analysis Which Impacts Increasing Re-Transaction Intentions", the authors draw the following research conclusions:

- This study found that perceived ease of use has a positive and insignificant effect on online shopping satisfaction (e-satisfaction).
- This study proves that perceived usefulness has a positive and significant effect on online shopping satisfaction (e-satisfaction).
- This study proves that perceived price has a positive and significant effect on online shopping satisfaction (e-satisfaction).
- This study proves that online service quality (e-service quality) has a positive and significant effect on online shopping satisfaction (e-satisfaction).

- This study proves that perceived ease of use has a positive and significant effect on the intention to return online shopping transactions (e-repurchase intention).
- This study found that perceived usefulness had a positive and insignificant effect on the intention to return online shopping transactions (e-repurchase intention).
- This study proves that perceived price has a positive and significant effect on the intention to return online shopping transactions (e-repurchase intention).
- This study found that online service quality (e-service quality) had a negative and insignificant effect on the intention to return online shopping transactions (e-repurchase intention).
- This study proves that online shopping satisfaction (e-satisfaction) has a positive and significant effect on the intention to return online shopping transactions (e-repurchase intention).
- This study found that online shopping satisfaction (e-satisfaction) did not mediate between perceived ease of use (perceived ease of use) and the intention to return online shopping transactions (e-repurchase intention).
- This study proves that online shopping satisfaction (e-satisfaction) mediates between Perceived Usefulness of online shopping transaction intentions (e-repurchase intention).
- This study proves that online shopping satisfaction (e-satisfaction) mediates between Perceived Price of Online Products (Perceived Price) on the intention to return online shopping transactions (e-repurchase intention).
- This study proves that online shopping satisfaction (e-satisfaction) mediates between online service quality (e-service quality) and online shopping transaction intentions (e-repurchase intention).
- Based on the research conclusions above, the authors take an important value, namely that the variables Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Price and E-Service Quality are important factors that positively influence customer satisfaction when shopping online which can have an impact on customer intentions to transact again.

SUGGESTION

Based on the results of the research conducted, the researcher has several practical suggestions for maintaining and increasing customer satisfaction and encouraging repeat transaction intentions as follows:

- The Shopee marketplace company must ensure that the quality of online services provided meets or even exceeds customer expectations. This can be achieved by ensuring fast product delivery, easy website navigation, smooth transaction processes and satisfying customer service by providing the right solutions, responsive and responsive to customer problems or every customer transaction.
- The Shopee marketplace company must offer competitive and fair prices so that customers are satisfied with the price they pay. This can be achieved

by continuing to consistently provide attractive and more discounts and promos to its customers periodically or in the context of certain events, such as Hari Raya or other special days, ensuring the price offered is comparable to the quality of the products and services provided. given, providing flexible payment options, such as installments or payments via e-wallet, to help reduce the customer's financial burden and establish good cooperation with suppliers and maintain the efficiency of Shopee's operational costs.

- The Shopee marketplace company must focus on developing features and services that can provide additional benefits that customers feel. This can be achieved by developing features such as the "chat to buy" or "instant checkout" features which can improve the ease of shopping and customer experience, maintain the quality of products and services provided meet or even exceed customer expectations, provide education to customers about features and services. available, so that customers can maximize the benefits they get from using the platform, conduct surveys and market research regularly to understand customer needs and wants, so that companies can continuously update their features and services according to customer needs and develop loyalty programs that provide additional benefits to customers who frequently shop on the platform so as to increase repeat transaction intentions and strengthen the relationship between the company and the customer.
- The Shopee marketplace company must optimize the Shopee application platform so that it is easy to use. This can be achieved by adopting the latest technology and features that make it easier for customers to search for products, evaluate products, and interact with sellers or other customers, has an attractive and intuitive appearance, can run smoothly on various devices and platforms, such as smartphones, tablets, and laptops , provide sufficient training and support to customers, especially for those who are new to using the Shopee application to better understand how to use the application and maximize their experience in shopping online and continue to monitor and evaluate the customer experience in using the Shopee application, so that they can identify problems or obstacles that may be encountered customer and take action to correct it.

ACADEMIC ADVICE

Based on the results of the research conducted, the researcher has several academic suggestions for research on similar topics as follows:

- In future research, it is suggested to expand the research area or take a different research area with different characteristics of the respondents so that the research sample is more accurate and can capture consumer perceptions in a comprehensive and in-depth manner.
- In future research, it is recommended to conduct further research to understand more deeply the variables with negative results because these variables can still be developed in the future.

- In future research, further research can be done by modifying the research model by adding other variables not found in this study, for example the variable trust, brand ambassador, perceived enjoyment, e-word of mouth, brand image, perceived risk, product quality or promotion .

REFERENCES

- [1]. Adinata, K. J., & Yasa, N. N. K. (2018). Pengaruh Kepercayaan, Persepsi Harga, Dan Sikap Terhadap Niat Beli Kembali Di Situs Lazada. E-Jurnal Manajemen Universitas Udayana, 7(8), 4153. <https://doi.org/10.24843/ejmunud.2018.v07.i08.p05>
- [2]. Ali, Hapzi dan Nandan Limakrisna. (2013). *Metodologi Penelitian*. Deepublish. Yogyakarta
- [3]. Alvarez-Risco A., Quipuzco-Chicata L., & Escudero-Cipriani C. (2022). Determinants of Online Repurchase Intention in Covid-19 Times: Evidence from an Emerging Economy. *Lecturas de Economía*, 96, 101-143. <https://doi.org/10.17533/udea.le.n96a342>
- [4]. Antwi, Samuel (2021). I just like this e-Retailer?: Understanding online consumers repurchase intention from relationship quality perspective, *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 61, 102568, ISSN 0969-6989, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2021.102568>.
- [5]. APJII (Asosiasi Penyelenggara Jasa Internet Indonesia). (2022). *Profil Internet Indonesia 2022*. Jakarta: APJII.
- [6]. Ariani, S., Firdaus, M. R., & Hairudinor (2019). Analysis of The Influence of Service Quality, Price, Trust and Corporate Image on Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty in PT. Pos Indonesia Banjarmasin. *European Journal of Management and Marketing Studies*. 4(2). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3462711>
- [7]. Armahadyani (2018). Pengaruh harga, promosi dan kualitas pelayanan terhadap keputusan pembelian konsumen pada kedai makan pa'mur karawang. *Jurnal Manajemen & Bisnis Kreatif*, 3(2). <https://doi.org/10.36805/manajemen.v3i2.253>.
- [8]. Asmarina, N. L. P. G. M., Yasa, N. N. K., & Ekawati, N. W. (2022). The Role of Satisfaction in Mediating the Effect of Perceived Ease of Use and Perceived Usefulness on Purchase Intention: Study on Bukalapak Marketplace's Customer in Bali Province. *International Research Journal of Management, IT & Social Sciences*, 9(5), 690-706. <https://doi.org/10.21744/irjmis.v9n5.2164>
- [9]. Basyar, K., & Sanaji (2018). Pengaruh Persepsi Kemudahan dan Persepsi Manfaat Terhadap Niat Beli Ulang Secara Online Dengan Kepuasan Sebagai Variabel Intervening. *Bisnis dan Manajemen*, 8(2), DOI:10.26740/bisma.v8n2.p204-217
- [10]. Bhattacharjee, A. (2001). Understanding Information System Continuance: An Expectation-Confirmation Model. *Management Information System*, 25(3), 351-370
- [11]. Blut, M. (2016). E-Service Quality: Development of a Hierarchical Model. *Journal of Retailing*, 92(4), 500–517. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretai.2016.09.002>
- [12]. Boer, R. F. (2018). Reputation Communication of Online Companies. *Jurnal Komunikasi Ikatan Sarjana Komunikasi Indonesia*, 3(1), 36–44. <https://doi.org/10.25008/jkiski.v3i1.147>
- [13]. Ching, K. C., Hasan, Z. R. A. & Hasan, N. A. (2021). Factors Influencing Consumers in Using Shopee for Online Purchase Intention in East Coast Malaysia. *Journal of Undergraduate Research*, 3(1), 45-56. <http://doi.org/10.46754/umtjur.2021.01.006>
- [14]. Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived Usefulness Percived Ease of Use and User Acceptance of Information Technology. *MIS Quarterly: Management Information Systems*, 13(3), 319–339. <https://doi.org/10.2307/249008>
- [15]. Davis, F. D., Bagozzi, R. P., & Warshaw, P. R. (1989). User Acceptance of Computer Technology: A Comparison of Two Theoretical Models. *Management Science*, 35(8), 982–1003. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.35.8.982>
- [16]. Dewi, C. R. A., Yasa, N. N. K., Giantari, I. G. A. K., Sukawati, T. G. R., Setiawan, P. Y., & Setini, M. (2020). The Effect of Security, Trust and Ease of Use towards Repurchase Intentions Mediated by E-satisfaction on Online Travel Agent. *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems*, 12(8), 45-56. <http://doi.org/10.46754/umtjur.2021.01.006>
- [17]. Fallis, A. (2013). Pengertian Dasar Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, 53(9), 1689–1699. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324.004>
- [18]. Febriani, N. M. A., & Ardani, I. G. A. K. S. (2021). The Influence of Customer Experience, Ease of Use, and Trust on Repurchase Intention (Case Study of Tokopedia Consumers in Denpasar). *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 5(2), 378-383.
- [19]. Ferdianto, R., & Hendar. (2022). The Role of Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use in Increasing Repurchase Intention in the Era of the Covid-19 Pandemic. *Research Horizon*, 2(2), 313-329.
- [20]. Grace, E., Sinaga, O. S., Silalahi, M., Ambarita, M. H. & Simatupang. S. (2022). Harga dan Kualitas Pelayanan Serta Pengaruhnya Terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan. *Buletin Poltanesa*, 23(1), <https://doi.org/10.51967/tanesa.v23i1.931>
- [21]. Hair, J. F., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2011). PLS-SEM: Indeed a silver bullet. *Journal of Marketing theory and Practice*, 19(2), 139-152.
- [22]. Hair, J. F., Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., & Mena, J. A. (2012). An assessment of the use of partial least squares structural equation modeling in marketing research. *Journal of the academy of marketing science*, 40(3), 414-433.

- [23]. Hair, J. F., Sarstedt, M., Hopkins, L., & G. Kuppelwieser, V. (2014). Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) An emerging tool in business research. *European Business Review*, 26(2), 106-121
- [24]. Hardiyanto, N. & Firdaus, A. (2021). Website Quality and the Role of Customer Satisfaction Toward Repurchase Intention: A Study of Indonesian E-Commerce. *Journal of Marketing Innovation*, 1(1), 62-77. DOI:10.35313/jmi.v1i01.15.
- [25]. Hasman, P. C. H., Ginting, P., & Rini, S. E. (2019). The influence of e-service quality on e-satisfaction and its impact on repurchase intention in using e-commerce applications on students of Universitas Sumatera Utara. *International Journal of Research and Review*, 6(10),299-307
- [26]. Iprice.co.id. (2022). The Map of E-commerce in Indonesia. IPrice Group. <https://iprice.co.id/insights/mapofecommerce/en/>
- [27]. Ipsos. (2022). Hasil Riset Ipsos: Shopee jadi E-Commerce yang Paling Banyak Digunakan pada 2021. Retrieved from <https://money.kompas.com/read/2022/01/31/204500426/hasil-riset-ipsos-shopee-jadi-e-commerce-yang-paling-banyak-digunakan-pada?page=all>
- [28]. Iqbal, S., Bhatti, Z. A., & Khan, M. N. (2018). Assessing e-service quality of B2C sites: a proposed framework. *International Journal of Information Technology*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41870-018-0247-4>
- [29]. Jatimoyo, D., Rohman, F., & Djazuli, A. (2021). "The Effect of Perceived Ease of Use on Continuance Intention through Perceived Usefulness and Trust." *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science* (2147- 4478) 10(4): 430–437
- [30]. Jaya, W., Arifin, R., & Slamet, A. R. (2021). Pengaruh Kualitas Pelayanan, Kualitas Produk, Harga, dan Lokasi terhadap Kepuasan Konsumen (Studi Kasus pada Konsumen Kafe Family Kopi di Malang). *E-Jurnal Riset Manajemen*, 10(1), 46–62.
- [31]. Juniwati, & Sumiyati. (2020). The Role of Satisfaction in Mediating the Effect of e-Service Convenience, Security, and Trust on Repurchase Intention in the Marketplace Case study: Shopee Marketplace. *J. Mgt. Mkt. Review*, 5(2), 93 – 98.
- [32]. Kahar, A., Wardi, Y., & Patrisia, D. (2019). The Influence of Perceived of Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and Perceived Security on Repurchase Intention at Tokopedia.com. *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*, 64(1), 429–438. <https://doi.org/10.2991/piceeba2-18.2019.20>
- [33]. Kotler, P. & Armstrong, G. (2011). *Manajemen Pemasaran*. Jilid 2. Bumi Aksara. Jakarta
- [34]. Kotler, P. & Kevin L. Keller (2009). *Manajemen Pemasaran*. Jilid I. Edisi Ketiga Belas. Erlangga. Jakarta
- [35]. Kristanto, H., & Firdausy, C.M. (2021). Pengaruh perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, attitude toward using dan sales promotion terhadap repurchase intention tiket bioskop pengguna aplikasi tix-id. *Manajemen Bisnis dan Kewirausahaan* 5(3).
- [36]. Liang, L. J., Choi, H. C., & Joppe, M. (2018). Exploring the relationship between satisfaction, trust and switching intention, repurchase intention in the context of Airbnb. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 69(November 2017), 41–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2017.10.015>
- [37]. Liao, C, Palvia, P., and Chen, J. L. (2009) Information Technology Adoption Behavior Life Cycle: Toward a Technology Continuance Theory (TCT). *International Journal of Information Management*, 29(4), 309-320. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2009.03.004>
- [38]. Miao, M., Jalees, T., Zaman, S.I., Khan, S., Hanif, N.U. & Javed, M.K. (2021). The influence of e-customer satisfaction, e-trust and perceived value on consumer's repurchase intention in B2C e-commerce segment. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics, ahead-of-print(ahead-of-print)*, 1-17
- [39]. Mirantheni, A., & Idris. (2017). Pengaruh Citra Perusahaan, Kualitas Layanan, dan Persepsi Harga terhadap Minat Beli Ulang melalui Kepuasan Pelanggan sebagai Variabel Intervening (Studi pada penumpang New Atlas Taksi Semarang). *Diponegoro Journal of Management*, 6(3), 1–8. <http://ejournal-s1.undip.ac.id/index.php/dbr>
- [40]. McCord, M. (2006). Technology acceptance model. *Handbook of Research on Electronic Surveys and Measurements*, 306–308. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-59140-792-8.ch038>
- [41]. Musdalifah, M. & Noor, M. (2019). Pengaruh kualitas pelayanan dan harga terhadap kepuasan pelanggan jasa transportasi online (go-jek). *Sebatik*, 23(2), pp. 498-504. Available at: <https://jurnal.wicida.ac.id/index.php/sebatik/article/view/804> (Accessed: 30November2022).
- [42]. Napitupulu, D. H. (2019). Pengaruh Harga Dan Kualitas Produk Terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan. *Jurnal Manajemen Bisnis Krisnadwipayana*, 7(1), 233–240. <https://doi.org/10.35137/jmbk.v7i1.248>.
- [43]. Oktarini, M. A. S. & Wardana, I. M. (2021). The Role of Customer Satisfaction to Mediate the Effect of Perceived Ease of Use and Perceived Enjoyment on Repurchase Intention. *E-Jurnal Manajemen Unud*, 7(4), 2041-2072. <https://doi.org/10.24843/EJMUNUD.2018.v7.i04.p12>
- [44]. Pee, L. G., Jiang, J., & Klein, G. (2018). Signaling effect of website usability on repurchase intention. *International Journal of Information Management*, 39, 228-241. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2017.12.010>
- [45]. Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V. A., & Malhotra, A. (2005). ES-QUAL: A multiple-item scale for assessing electronic service quality. *Journal of Service Research*, 7(3), 213-233.
- [46]. Prasetya, I. A. & Suwitho (2022). Pengaruh Persepsi Kemudahan dan Manfaat Terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan dan Minat Pembelian Ulang Pada Aplikasi Shopee. *Jurnal Ilmu dan Riset Manajemen*, 11 (9), e-ISSN: 2461-0593.

- [47]. Pratiwi, I., & Andalia, W. (2018). Perancangan Model Keputusan Multikriteria Pemilihan Layanan E-Commerce Untuk Kepuasan Pelanggan. *Seminar Nasional Sains Dan Teknologi 2018*, 1–10. <https://jurnal.umj.ac.id/index.php/semnastek/article/view/3505/2638>.
- [48]. Puryanto, B. S. D. (2021). *Pengaruh Harga, Kualitas Pelayanan dan Kualitas Produk terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan di E-Commerce Shopee*. Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta.
- [49]. Ramadiani, R. (2010). *Sem Dan Lisrel Untuk Analisis Multivariate*. <http://ejournal.unsri.ac.id/index.php/jsi/index>
- [50]. Riadi, E. (2018). *Statistik SEM structural equation modeling dengan Lisrel*. CV Andi Offset.
- [51]. Riki Wijayajaya, H., & Tri Astuti, S. R. (2018). The Effect of Trust and Brand Image to Repurchase Intention in Online Shopping. *KnE Social Sciences*, 3(10), 915. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v3i10.3182>
- [52]. Rita, P., Oliveira, T. & Farisa, A. (2019). The impact of E-Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction on Customer Behavior in Online Shopping, *Heliyon*, 5(10), e02690, ISSN 2405-8440, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2019. e02690>.
- [53]. Rulfiansah, F. F. & Seno, A. H. D. (2020). Pengaruh Harga Dan Kualitas Produk Terhadap Kepuasan Konsumen (Studi Pada Konsumen Rainbow Creative Semarang). *Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi Bisnis*, 9 (4), 389-401. <https://doi.org/10.14710/jiab.2020.28226>
- [54]. Santona, E., Sudaryanto, & Afandi, M. F. (2021). Marketplace's Perceived Ease of Use, Price and Promotion on Consumer's Repurchase Interest. *Jurnal Bisnis dan Manajemen*, 15(3), 200-207. <https://doi.org/10.19184/bisma.v15i3.28146>
- [55]. Sawitri, N.L.P.W., & Giantri, I.G.A.K. (2020). The Role of Trust Mediates the Effect of Perceived Ease of Use and Perceived Usefulness on Online Repurchase Intention. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)* 4(1): 374–81. <http://www.ajhssr.com/>.
- [56]. Schiffman, Leon G., & Leslie L. Kanuk. (2000). *Consumer Behavior*, Seventh Edition. New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- [57]. Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2016). *Research Methods for Business: A Skill-Building Approach* (7 ed.). West Sussex: John Wiley & Sons Ltd.
- [58]. Sintya, I. L., Lapian, S.L.H.V.J. Lapian, & Maruntu, M.M. (2018). Pengaruh Harga Dan Kualitas Layanan Terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan Jasa Transportasi Gojek Online Pada Mahasiswa FEB Unsrat Manado. *Jurnal Riset Ekonomi, Manajemen, Bisnis dan Akuntansi*, 6 (3), 1778-1787. <https://doi.org/10.35794/emba.v6i3.20462>
- [59]. Sullivan, Y. W., & Kim, D. J. (2018). Assessing the effects of consumers' product evaluations and trust on repurchase intention in e-commerce environments. *International Journal of Information Management*, 39(December 2017), 199–219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2017.12.008>
- [60]. Sumargono. (2011). Sejarah Perkembangan Internet Dan Kebutuhan Informasi Era Online Dalam Dunia Pendidikan. *TEKNOLOGI: Jurnal Ilmiah Sistem Informasi*. Vol.1. No.1.
- [61]. Statista. (2019). *Number of orders on Shopee from 1st quarter 2020 to 3rd quarter 2022*. Retrieved from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1118061/shopee-number-of-orders/>
- [62]. Syaharani, D. P. & Yasa, N. N. K. (2022). The Role of Trust as Mediation between Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use on Repurchase Intention. *European Journal of Development Studies*, ISSN: 2736-660X. DOI: 10.24018/ejdevelop.2022.2.3.91
- [63]. Tandon, U., Kiran, R. and Sah, A.N. (2017), Analyzing Customer Satisfaction: Users Perspective Towards Online Shopping, *Nankai Business Review International*, 8(3), 266-288. <https://doi.org/10.1108/NBRI-04-2016-0012>
- [64]. Tandon, U., Kiran, R., & Sah, A. N. (2017). Customer Satisfaction as Mediator Between Website Service Quality and Repurchase Intention: An Emerging Economy Case. *Service Science*, 9(2), 106-120. <https://doi.org/10.1287/serv.2016.0159>
- [65]. Tobagus, A. (2018). Pengaruh E-service quality terhadap e-satisfaction pada pengguna di situs Tokopedia. *Agora*, 6(1),1-10.
- [66]. Topbrandaward. (2022). Top Brand Index Fase 2 2022. Retrieved from https://www.topbrandaward.com/top_brand_index
- [67]. Trivedi, S.K. & Yadav, M. (2020). "Repurchase intentions in Y generation: mediation of trust and e-satisfaction", *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 38(4), 401-415. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MIP-02-2019-0072>
- [68]. Tunnufus, Zakiyya, Wulandari, A. (2019). Pengaruh Harga Dan Jenis Media Promosi Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Online Pada E-Commerce Shopee Di Kabupaten Lebak. *The Asia Pacific; Journal of Management Studies*, 6(1), 29–40. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.55171/v6i1.326>
- [69]. Venkatesh, V. & Davis, F. D. (1996). "A Model of the Antecedents of Perceived Ease of Use: Development and Test." *Decision Sciences* 27, 3: pp.451-470.
- [70]. Venkatesh, V., & Davis, F. D. (2000). A theoretical extension of the technology acceptance model: Four longitudinal field studies. *Management science*, 46(2), 186-204.
- [71]. Wafiyah, R. S. & Kusumadewi, N. M. W. (2021). The Effect of Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and Trust on Repurchase Intention on E-Commerce Shopee. *IJISSET - International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering & Technology*, 8(7), ISSN (Online) 2348 – 7968.
- [72]. Weng, G. S., Zailani, S., Iranmanesh, M., & Hyun, S. S. (2017). Mobile Taxi Booking Application Service's Continuance Usage Intention by Users. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 57, 207-216. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2017.07.023>

- [73]. Widyaastuti, T. (2019). Pengaruh Harga dan Kualitas Produk Terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan Tempe. *Jurnal Ecodemica*, 7(1), 233–240. <https://doi.org/10.35137/jmbk.v7i1.248>
- [74]. Wilson, N. (2019). The Impact of Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease-of Use Toward Repurchase Intention in the Indonesian E-Commerce Industry.” *Jurnal Manajemen Indonesia* 19(3): 241-249. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jmi.v19i3.2412>
- [75]. Wilson, N., Alvita, M. & Wibisono, J. (2021). The Effect of Perceived Ease of Use and Perceived Security Toward Satisfaction and Repurchase Intention. *Jurnal Muara Ilmu Ekonomi dan Bisnis* 5(1): 145. <https://doi.org/10.24912/jmieb.v5i1.10489>
- [76]. Wiwoho, G. (2019). Pengaruh Perceived Usefulness Dan Perceived Ease of Use Terhadap Customer Satisfaction Dan Repurchase Intention Pengguna Aplikasi Ovo. *Fokus Bisnis: Media Pengkajian Manajemen dan Akuntansi* 18(1): 53–61. <https://doi.org/10.32639/fokusbisnis.v18i1.530>
- [77]. Yanico, Y., & Keni, K. (2021). Perceived Ease of Use, Trust, Dan Customer Satisfaction Sebagai Prediktor Terhadap Repurchase Intention. *Jurnal Manajemen Maranatha* 20(2): 107–18. <https://doi.org/10.28932/jmm.v20i2.3244>
- [78]. Zhang, Y., Fang, Y., Wei, K. K., Ramsey, E., McCole, P., & Chen, H. (2011). Repurchase intention in B2C e-commerce - A relationship quality perspective. *Information and Management*, 48(6), 192–200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2011.05.003>